

OPTIMIZING DEEP LEARNING COMPONENTS FOR ENHANCEMENT OF SOIL MOISTURE PREDICTION MODELS FROM REMOTE SENSING DATA

¹Pascal Yamakili, ²Mrindoko Nicholas & ³Kenedy Greyson

*^{1,2} Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Mbeya University of Science and Technology,
Tanzania

³Department of Electronics and Telecommunications Engineering, Dar es Salaam Institute of Technology,
Tanzania

*¹Correspond Author: pacoyamakilh@gmail.com, nicholausmrindoko@gmail.com

kenedyaliila@yahoo.com

Abstract

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Designing deep learning models for remote sensing based soil moisture estimation is a complex task that requires careful selection of architectural components to achieve high accuracy and generalization. This study aims to evaluate the impact of different deep learning configurations on soil moisture prediction performance. Four model variants were developed, each exploring distinct architectural features, including the presence or absence of feature fusion, residual connections, and squeeze and excitation attention blocks. The study collected dataset size of 2200 splitted at the ratio of 70% used for training while 15% used for validation and the remaining 15% was used for testing. All models were trained on the same dataset using identical hyperparameters to ensure a fair comparison. Their performance was assessed using three standard regression metrics: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). Among the tested models, the best-performing variant achieved an RMSE of 0.0117 (1.17%), MAE of 0.0148 (1.48%), and an R^2 of 0.8639 consistently outperforming several baseline models reported in existing literature. These findings demonstrate competitive performance of targeted architectural enhancements in improving deep learning based soil moisture estimation and offer a valuable benchmark for future research in this domain.

Keywords: Soil moisture, Data fusion, Residual learning, , squeeze and excitation

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of soil moisture is vital for agriculture, hydrology, land management, and climate studies, supporting informed decision-making in areas such as irrigation planning, flood and drought

forecasting, and environmental monitoring (Brocca et al., 2010; Editors et al., 2023; Rabiei et al., 2025; Tang et al., 2022) The spatial distribution of soil moisture serves as a key indicator for optimizing water resource management and enhancing disaster preparedness. Traditional soil moisture measurement methods fall

Corresponding author's email: pacoyamakilh@gmail.com

website: www.academyjsekad.edu.ng

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into two broad categories: point-based sensors and remote sensing approaches. While point-based methods offer high temporal resolution and precision at specific locations, they are limited in spatial coverage and often fail to represent variability across heterogeneous landscapes. Prior studies have revealed significant spatial variability in soil moisture, even within seemingly homogeneous environments (Dari et al., 2019). For instance, sensor-based studies have recorded variations ranging from $0.036 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ at a 2.5 m scale to $0.071 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ at a 50 km scale, indicating that heterogeneity increases with spatial extent (Famiglietti et al., 2008).

Remote sensing techniques, particularly satellite based platforms, offer broader spatial coverage but often suffer from uneven spatial resolution, which reduces the precision of soil moisture estimates (Rasheed et al., 2022). To address these limitations, recent research has turned to machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques such as Transformer models and hybrid CNN-LSTM networks which have shown promise in capturing nonlinear relationships in environmental data (Perera et al., 2025). However, deep learning techniques provides an improved option to machine learning (Dargan et al., 2019). Machine learning techniques for soil moisture prediction are limited by their reliance on manual feature engineering, reduced ability to capture complex nonlinear relationships, weak modeling of spatial and temporal dependencies, and lower scalability with high-dimensional remote sensing data (Malik, 2020). They often require pre-processed inputs, show limited generalization across regions, and tend to saturate in performance as data volume increases, whereas deep learning techniques overcome these limitations through automatic feature learning, stronger spatiotemporal representation, and better utilization of large, data-rich datasets.

Despite these advances from ML to DL, accurately estimating soil moisture remains a complex challenge, especially in diverse and data scarce environments. Therefore, ongoing assessment of DL models under different configurations and environmental conditions is essential.

In this context, this study introduces an innovative deep learning architecture tailored for soil moisture prediction using remote sensing data. The Models introduced under this study incorporates. Objective of the study is to explicitly evaluates the individual and combined effects of feature fusion, residual connections, and squeeze-and-excitation mechanisms on image-based soil moisture estimation accuracy. Also the use of advanced DL architectural components such as residual connections and attention

based feature fusion and squeeze and excitations mechanisms to improve prediction accuracy and spatial resolution. Trained and evaluated on consistent datasets, the Model demonstrates improved performance over traditional and simpler DL models. This research contributes to the growing body of work in remote sensing-driven environmental modelling by offering a scalable and robust framework for large-scale soil moisture monitoring, with particular relevance for semi-arid regions.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent technological advancement, apart from traditional methods for soil moisture measurement, that include in situ measurement and physical hydrological and statistical methods, machine learning and deep learning techniques have gained significant attention for soil moisture prediction. Deep learning soil moisture prediction models have arose as powerful tools due to their capability to automatically extract hierarchical features and model complex nonlinear dependencies. This section highlights some noticed deep learning studies related to this study by highlighting their strength and their limitaions as well. The works cited are used as bluepring for enhancement of this current study.

A deep learning model to forecast the daily soil moisture values by using time series of climate and radar satellite data along with the soil type and topographic data is presented by Celik et al., 2022. One of the main strength of the model was trained with static and dynamic features that influence sm retrieval. Furthermore the model developed predict daily soil moisture with high accuracy ($r^2 \approx 0.87$ and low error metrics), highlighting the strength of multi source data fusion and temporal modeling for capturing complex soil atmosphere interactions. Data fusion is one of the techniques employed in this study for architectural improvement of performance.

An innovative deep learning model with Residual-EnDecode-Feedforward Attention Mechanism-Long Short-Term Memory (REDF-LSTM) was designed to overcome the high uncertainty challenges faced by traditional soil moisture prediction methods. The model integrated a residual learning encoder-decoder LSTM layer, enhanced LSTM layers, and feedforward attention. The model was designed to capture deep features of time series data and optimizes the model's ability to identify key influencing factors, including land surface features, atmospheric conditions, and other static environmental variables (X. Li et al., 2024). With the use of residual and attention mechanism the

study drew more attention on using and optimizing several architectural components in deep learning studies. Further studies in (Liu et al., 2025) developed a model for soil moisture that integrates residual learning into an encoder-decoder LSTM architecture, along with a feedforward attention mechanism. Residual learning also aimed to skip connections that help tackle vanishing gradients and deepen feature extraction for complex soil moisture dynamics.

Feature fusion is another important architectural mechanism that enhances precise soil moisture prediction with spatial and temporal. A study in Lamichhane et al., 2025, presents a model for surface soil moisture prediction using multimodal remote sensing data fusion and machine learning algorithms in semi-arid agricultural regions. It employs fusion of SAR, optical, and derived features to improve surface prediction significantly compared to single-source inputs. The technique of feature fusion was also applied by S. Li et al., 2025, for the fusion of Multispectral and thermal infrared data, Auxiliary environmental variables and Combinations of multiple input scenarios for the Regional Soil Moisture Estimation Leveraging Multi-Source Data Fusion and Automated Machine Learning.

Generally, the literature has highlighted the potential of using architectural components such as residual learning and excitation enhancement together with feature fusion mechanism for designing ML and DL models for improving results. The current study has also relied on combination of these components for optimization of performance of deep learning model for soil moisture prediction.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Dataset collection and processing

In this study, the datasets collected comprised of Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar images with vertical transmit and vertical receive (SAR_VV) polarization. Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar images with vertical transmit and horizontal receive (SAR_VH) polarization were also included. RGB true color optical images from Sentinel-2 and normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) images calculated from Sentinel-2's near-infrared (B8) and red (B4) bands were collected too. Sentinel-1 (S1A and S1B) provides C-band SAR imagery at 5.5405 GHz with dual-polarization capabilities, while Sentinel-2 (S2A and S2B) offers multispectral optical imagery across 13 spectral bands (Santos et al., 2023). Data collected was in range of January 1, 2017, to March 1, 2024. The images were retrieved using Google Earth Engine with random geographic coordinates. The

dataset covers tropical environments with latitudes between 40°S and 40°N in the WGS84 coordinate system.

3.2 Size of the area and dataset resolution

For the context of this study, the data which were retrieved were images which cover a scene of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (approximately $11\text{km} \times 11\text{km}$ at the equator). All images were clipped to 512×512 pixels. The dataset consists of 2200 distinct geographic locations, with corresponding images in each of the four data types described. The resolution of data obtained from Sentinel-1 for SAR images was $10\text{m} \times 10\text{m}$ resolution (Level-1 Ground Range Detected format) and from Sentinel-2 for optical imagery varies by band (10m, 20m, and 60m), but the RGB bands used (B2, B3, B4) which had 10m resolution.

Finally, all images were processed and stored as GeoTIFF files to preserve geographic information (Limp, 1999). The SAR images underwent radiometric calibration and terrain correction (orthorectification). The optical images were filtered to ensure minimal cloud interference (less than 5% cloud cover) (Wang et al., 2022).

3.2 Design of deep learning surface soil moisture prediction models algorithm

A total of four Model variants were designed and evaluated, all trained using identical dataset, identical parameters and the same learning rate of 0.001, batch size of 20, and 25 training epochs. The aim of designing the four variants was step by step testing how the feature fusion in data fusion and Deep Learning components specifically RL and SE would affect the performance of designed Model and finally, recommend the improved Model for soil moisture prediction. The first variant involved a simplified, conventional CNN architecture without feature fusion mechanisms (*no_fusion*). The second variant excluded both SE blocks and residual connections (*referred to as no_se_no_residual*), aiming to isolate the effect of RL and SE components but included feature fusion. The aim of this setup was to experimentally observe the impact of feature fusion. The third setup included the RL with feature fusion to obtain the variant (*referred to as with_residual*). The aim of this variant was to check the impact of integrating residual learning (residual connections) and feature fusion to improve performance of the designed Model. Finally, the fourth variant (*referred to as with_se_residual*), retained residual connections but introduced the SE blocks to evaluate the contribution of SE attention.

With each variant, the Model was trained and evaluated using key three metrics which included Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Coefficient of Determination (R^2). Table 1 compares the results of Model Variants in term of performance under described Metrics.

The feature fusion in the model variants was designed by employing multi-sensor **data fusion** and by combining three complementary remote sensing data sources: NDVI (vegetation index), SAR VH, and SAR VV polarization backscatter images (Fig.

1). Each data source is preprocessed through min-max normalization to standardize values between 0-1 (Equation 1).

$$I_{norm} = \frac{I - \min(I)}{\max(I) - \min(I)}$$

The normalized images are stacked to create a unified 3-channel feature representation that captures vegetation characteristics (NDVI) and soil surface properties (SAR backscatter). This fusion approach leverages the complementary nature of optical and microwave remote sensing data to improve soil moisture estimation (Schalie et al., 2018). The Model's target variable is derived from ground truth measurements, calculated as the average of water percentage and vegetation percentage, serving as a proxy for soil moisture content's

Figure 1. Data Fusion and Feature architecture for the proposed Model

Residual learning techniques were introduced in the model variants **with_residual** and **with_se_residual**, which could help train deep neural networks by mitigating the vanishing gradient problem. It introduces shortcut connections that bypass one or more layers, allowing the Model to learn identity mappings where necessary. The residual function structure is given by Equation 2.

$$Y = F(X) + X \text{ (Liitiäinen et al., 2009)} \quad (2)$$

where $F(X)$ represents the convolution operations and (X) is the input. The network optimizes training efficiency and improves gradient flow by learning residual functions instead of direct mappings. The **with_se_residual** model variant incorporated the Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) mechanism, enhancing feature representations by adaptively recalibrating

channel-wise feature responses. This was done in two main steps by employing Squeeze and Excitations mechanisms: In Squeeze mechanism global average pooling computes channel importance. Equation 3 depicts SE function where this operation aggregates spatial information into a compact channel descriptor..

$$SE = \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W X_{c,i,j} \quad \text{for } c=1 \dots\dots, C$$

(Jin et al., 2022) (3)

where ($X_{c,i,j}$) represents the feature map activation at

spatial location (i, j) for the channel (c). and then in the excitation mechanism fully connected layers with non-linearity learn interdependencies between channels, producing scale factors to modulate feature maps as seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Designed Deep Learning Algorithm for Surface Soil Moisture prediction incorporating data fusion, RL and SE

The SE block improves feature discrimination and robustness in soil moisture estimation by dynamically adjusting feature map activations. Generally, SE mechanism are added to improve the performance of usual deep CNN by automatically fusing the channel-wise spatial information and inter-channel dependencies. By incorporating data fusion mechanism with SE mechanism, the Model was

expected to improve accuracy and address the spatial viability to the satellite datasets in predicting an area's Moisture (Xiang et al., 2022). Fig. 2 illustrate the entire architecture of the designed Model.

The model illustrated in Fig. 2 is a deeper residual CNN composed of four sequential residual blocks with progressive channel expansion

(3→64→128→256→256). Each residual block contains two 3×3 convolutional layers, batch normalization, ReLU activation, skip connections (with 1×1 projection when required), and an embedded squeeze-and-excitation (SE) module using a reduction ratio of 16. Global average pooling is applied before a fully connected regression head (256→128→1) with dropout (0.5). The architecture contains over 2 million trainable parameters, making it substantially deeper and more expressive than the baseline CNN variants. All models were trained using the Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001, MSE loss) on an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU with 16 GB memory, and training for 100 epochs required a few hours to converge.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The impact of feature fusion

At first, two models were evaluated. The first was a baseline convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture without any feature fusion mechanisms, referred to as *no_fusion*, and the second was an enhanced model incorporating feature fusion techniques, referred to as *no_se_no_residual*. The latter aimed to investigate the effectiveness of integrating multi-sensor data and feature fusion specifically integrated Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), RGB, and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) within the CNN framework. Then performance assessment was conducted using three regression metrics, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). As illustrated in Fig. 3, the feature fusion model (*no_se_no_residual*) consistently outperformed the baseline (*no_fusion*) across all evaluation metrics. Notably, it achieved lower MAE and RMSE values and a higher R^2 score, indicating improved prediction accuracy and model robustness. These results demonstrate the value of incorporating feature fusion mechanisms in CNN architectures, particularly when utilizing heterogeneous remote sensing data sources. The improved performance of the fusion based Model underscores the potential of multi-sensor data integration to enhance learning outcomes in Earth observation and related domains (Sahoo, 2024; Zhu et al., 2025).

4.2 The impact of residual learning

After comparing a conventional convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture without any feature fusion mechanisms, and an enhanced model incorporating feature fusion techniques, an additional

Model incorporating Residual Learning and feature fusion (referred as *with_residual*) was also trained under similar grounds. The aim of deploying RL was to find out if the Model can gain accuracy from considerable training parameters and datasets. As hypotheses suggested, the resulting Model (*with_residual*) outperformed performance of previous Model variants specifically the CNN architecture and the improved Model with feature fusion (*no_fusion* and *no_se_no_residual*) as shown in Table 1. Again the Model achieved lower MAE and RMSE values and a higher R^2 score, indicating improved prediction accuracy and model robustness.

4.3 The impact of squeeze and excitation

The final model configuration, which integrated Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) blocks following feature fusion and residual learning (referred to as *with_se_residual*), demonstrated the best overall performance across several evaluation metrics. This final model variant outperformed all previous configurations. The Model achieved a Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of **0.0117 (1.17%)**, the lowest among all tested setups (see Table 1 results across variants). RMSE quantifies the average difference between predicted and actual values; thus, a lower RMSE signifies stronger agreement between model estimations and observed data. In addition to RMSE, the Model also yielded a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of **0.0148 (1.48%)**, further confirming its improved predictive accuracy.

Table 1: Performance Comparison between the designed Model variants

Variant setup	RMSE (m ³ /m ³ , %) ↓	MAE (m ³ /m ³ , %) ↓	R ² ↑
with_se_residual	0.0117 (1.17%)	0.0148 (1.48%)	0.8639
with_residual	0.0215 (2.15%)	0.0241 (2.41%)	0.8139
no_se_no_residual	0.0205 (2.05%)	0.0293 (2.93%)	0.7139
no_fusion	0.0296 (2.96%)	0.0318 (3.18%)	0.6839

These results indicate that the integration of Squeeze-and-Excitation blocks, in combination with feature fusion and residual learning, substantially enhanced model performance. Furthermore, the Model showed superior outcomes across other key evaluation, indicating consistent and reliable predictions which highlight the Model's strong alignment with observed data. The sequential integration of architectural components, particularly the final addition of SE blocks, contributed significantly to the enhanced predictive capability of the Model, making **with_se_residual** the most effective configuration among those tested. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, for root mean square error and mean absolute error respectively, highlights the performance reached by the metrics across the model variants.

Figure 3: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) across Model Variants

Figure 4: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) across Model Variants

3.4 Modal validation

Comparison with baseline Models was conducted by comparing the highest performing variant in this study (**with_se_residual**) against single-modality approaches and traditional regression techniques such as the one used Random Forest (Rodriguez et al.,2020; Carranza et al., 2021). A comparison was also made between the models that used techniques such as UNet-3D and many more, as stipulated in Table 2. The comparison is based on contextualizing the performance range of this study’s designed models to the broader literature on soil moisture estimation from remote sensing imagery datasets. The metrics used included Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Coefficient of Determination (R²). The designed Model (**with_se_residual**), significantly outperformed majority of baseline models (as shown in Table 2),

highlighting the advantage of integrating data (data fusion) and applying techniques such as Squeeze, excitation and Residual Learning. For instance, the *with_se_residual* Model achieved RMSE of **0.0117 (1.18%)** which is typically smaller than many baseline models outlined in Table 2. The implication of this is that, the designed Model is assured with better performance in Moisture determination.

Table 2: Comparison between better performing variant (with_se_residual) and baseline Frameworks

Algorithm (Type)	Dataset Source	MAE (m ³ /m ³ , %)	RMSE (m ³ /m ³ , %)	R ²
CNN (Deep Learning) (E. H. Hegazi et al., 2021)	Sentinel-1 SAR	0.0144 (1.44%)	0.0274 (2.74%)	0.8664
<i>with_se_residual</i> (This study) (Deep Learning)	Sentinel-2 (This study)	0.0148 (1.49%)	0.0117 (1.18%)	0.8639
CNN (Deep Learning)(E. H. ; Hegazi et al., 2023)	Sentinel-2	0.0277 (2.77%)	0.0418 (4.18%)	0.7094
ANN (Deep Learning) (Lee et al., 2022)	Sentinel-1 SAR	–	0.0476 (4.76%)	0.7056
Feed-forward ANN (Deep Learning)(Lee et al., 2022)	Sentinel-1+2	–	0.0400 (4.00%)	0.64
Random Forest (ML) (Lakra et al., 2024)	Sentinel-2	0.0343 (3.43%)	0.0595 (5.95%)	0.49
Random Forest (ML) (Shokati et al., 2024)	Sentinel-1 SAR	–	0.0706 (7.06%)	0.61

4.0 CONCLUSION

This study introduced an innovative multi-models remote sensing model with the algorithm for accurate soil moisture prediction by integrating the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and RGB satellite dataset. Through extensive validation using comparison with baseline models, the final designed and recommended model variant approach demonstrated significantly improved performance in terms of accuracy, spatial consistency, and temporal responsiveness. The Model has achieved better performance metrics in term of Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and coefficient of determination R^2 . The experimental results has shown applying Deep Learning techniques such as feature fusion, residual learning and Squeeze and excitation had a higher level of predictive performance substantially, compared to other to the conventional CNN models. This suggests by applying residual leaning, the model variants used the advantage of the technique, to combine and integrate multiple feature types, such as spectral, textural, and shape information enhancing accuracy and robustness compared to using single features. Similarly, the application of Squeeze and excitation (SE) blocks had enhanced better performanc in moisture detection by focusing on informative features and suppressing less useful ones, leading to improved accuracy and efficiency. By recalibrating channel-wise feature responses, SE blocks enabled models to learn more about the importance of different features, especially in complex sections. A comparative analysis made to the baseline model has exposed the potential of multi modal, data fusional, Squeeze and excitation with residual learning remote sensing as a powerful tool for large scale, real time soil moisture monitoring. This approach holds significant implications for agriculture, hydrology, and climate modeling applications, offering a scalable solution for regions with sparse ground measurements. The limitation of this study's model is that it was trained in term of datasets lied only 40°S and 40°N in the WGS84 coordinate system that means it was trained on data from a limited set of regions, which may reduce geographic generalization training and inference require substantial computational resources. Future studies may broaden datasets areas and should concentrate in areas of similar works by focusing more on designing models that could work closer to real time applications and incorporate additional data sources such as weather forecasts and land surface temperature collected from practical fields and experimented.

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6.0 COMPETING INTEREST

The authors state that none of their known financial conflicts or interpersonal connections might have had an impact on the work presented in this paper.

7.0 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this work.

8.0 ETHICAL STATEMENT

This material is the authors' own original work, which has not been previously published elsewhere.

REFERENCES:

- Brocca, L., Melone, F., Moramarco, T., & Morbidelli, R. (2010). Spatial-temporal variability of soil moisture and its estimation across scales. *Water Resources Research*, 46(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009WR008016>
- Carranza, C., Nolet, C., Peziz, M., & van der Ploeg, M. (2021). Root zone soil moisture estimation with Random Forest. *Journal of Hydrology*, 593, 125840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2020.125840>
- Celik, M. F., Isik, M. S., Yuzugullu, O., Fajraoui, N., Erten, E., Celik, M. F., Isik, M. S., Yuzugullu, O., Fajraoui, N., & Erten, E. (2022). Soil Moisture Prediction from Remote Sensing Images Coupled with Climate, Soil Texture and Topography via Deep Learning. *Remote Sensing* 2022, Vol. 14, 14(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS14215584>
- Dargan, S., Kumar, M., Ayyagari, M. R., & Kumar, G. (2019). A Survey of Deep Learning and Its Applications: A New Paradigm to Machine Learning. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 2019 27:4, 27(4), 1071–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11831-019-09344-W>
- Dari, J., Morbidelli, R., Saltalippi, C., Massari, C., & Brocca, L. (2019). Spatial-temporal variability of soil moisture: Addressing the monitoring at the catchment scale. *Journal of Hydrology*, 570,

- 436–444.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2019.01.014>
- Editors, A., Zhang, F., Wang, X., Kung, H., Lin, X., Stinchcomb, G. E., Yang, Z., He, Q., Miao, S., Wei, F., & Yu, M. (2023). Surface Soil Moisture Retrieval of China Using Multi-Source Data and Ensemble Learning. *Remote Sensing 2023, Vol. 15, Page 2786, 15(11), 2786*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/RS15112786>
- Famiglietti, J. S., Ryu, D., Berg, A. A., Rodell, M., & Jackson, T. J. (2008). Field observations of soil moisture variability across scales. *Water Resources Research, 44(1), 1–16*.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005804>
- Hegazi, E. H. ;, Samak, A. A. ;, Yang, L. ;, Huang, R. ;, Huang, J., Alexakis, D., Niedbała, G., Hegazi, E. H., Samak, A. A., Yang, L., Huang, R., & Huang, J. (2023). Prediction of Soil Moisture Content from Sentinel-2 Images Using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). *Agronomy 2023, Vol. 13, Page 656, 13(3), 656*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/AGRONOMY13030656>
- Hegazi, E. H., Yang, L., & Huang, J. (2021). A convolutional neural network algorithm for soil moisture prediction from sentinel-1 SAR images. *Remote Sensing, 13(24)*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/RS13244964>
- Jin, X., Xie, Y., Wei, X. S., Zhao, B. R., Chen, Z. M., & Tan, X. (2022). Delving deep into spatial pooling for squeeze-and-excitation networks. *Pattern Recognition, 121, 108159*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PATCOG.2021.108159>
- Lakra, D., Pipil, S., Srivastava, P. K., Singh, S. K., Gupta, M., & Prasad, R. (2024). Soil moisture retrieval over agricultural region through machine learning and sentinel 1 observations. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing, 5, 1513620*.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FRSEN.2024.1513620>
 BIBTEX
- Lamichhane, M., Mehan, S., & Mankin, K. R. (2025). Surface soil moisture prediction using multimodal remote sensing data fusion and machine learning algorithms in semi-arid agricultural region. *Science of Remote Sensing, 12, 100255*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SRS.2025.100255>
- Lee, S., Hwang, E., Lee, H., Chung, J., Lee, Y., Kim, J., Jung, C., & Kim, S. (2022). Soil Moisture Content Estimation Based on Sentinel-1 SAR Imagery Using an Artificial Neural Network and Hydrological Components. *Remote Sensing 2022, Vol. 14, Page 465, 14(3), 465*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/RS14030465>
- Li, S., Zhu, P., Song, N., Li, C., Wang, J., Li, S., Zhu, P., Song, N., Li, C., & Wang, J. (2025). Regional Soil Moisture Estimation Leveraging Multi-Source Data Fusion and Automated Machine Learning. *Remote Sensing 2025, Vol. 17, 17(5)*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/RS17050837>
- Li, X., Zhang, Z., Li, Q., Zhu, J., Li, X., Zhang, Z., Li, Q., & Zhu, J. (2024). Enhancing Soil Moisture Forecasting Accuracy with REDF-LSTM: Integrating Residual En-Decoder and Feature Attention Mechanisms. *Water 2024, Vol. 16, 16(10)*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/W16101376>
- Liitiäinen, E., Verleysen, M., Corona, F., & Lendasse, A. (2009). Residual variance estimation in machine learning. *Neurocomputing, 72(16–18), 3692–3703*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUCOM.2009.07.004>
- Limp, W. F. (1999). Geographic Information Systems in Historic Preservation. *Archives and Museum Informatics 1999 13:3, 13(3), 325–340*.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1012472528263>
- Liu, Y., Fan, H., Jin, Y., Zhu, S., Liu, Y., Fan, H., Jin, Y., & Zhu, S. (2025). Reconstruction of SMAP Soil Moisture Data Based on Residual Autoencoder Network with Convolutional Feature Extraction. *Remote Sensing 2025, Vol. 17, 17(22)*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/RS17223729>
- Malik, M. M. (2020). *A Hierarchy of Limitations in Machine Learning*.
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2002.05193>
- Perera, K. P. V. D. U. P., Lakmal, H. K. I. S., Fernando, K. J. P., & Nirmal, W. C. (2025). Hybrid Deep Learning for Portable Weather Forecasting: Real-Time Predictions Using CNN-LSTM-Transformer Models. *Proceedings - International Research Conference on Smart Computing and Systems Engineering, SCSE 2025*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/SCSE65633.2025.11031062>

- Rabiei, S., Babaeian, E., & Grunwald, S. (2025). Surface and Subsurface Soil Moisture Estimation Using Fusion of SMAP, NLDAS-2, and SOLUS100 Data with Deep Learning. *Remote Sensing 2025, Vol. 17, Page 659, 17(4)*, 659. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS17040659>
- Rasheed, M. W., Tang, J., Sarwar, A., Shah, S., Saddique, N., Khan, M. U., Imran Khan, M., Nawaz, S., Shamshiri, R. R., Aziz, M., & Sultan, M. (2022). Soil Moisture Measuring Techniques and Factors Affecting the Moisture Dynamics: A Comprehensive Review. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, *14(18)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141811538>
- Sahoo, S. (2024). Sensor Fusion and Virtual Sensor Design for Enhanced Multi-Sensor Data Accuracy in Autonomous Systems. *International Journal on Smart & Sustainable Intelligent Computing*, *1(2)*, 21–39. <https://doi.org/10.63503/J.IJSSIC.2024.31>
- Santos, E. P. dos, Moreira, M. C., Fernandes-Filho, E. I., Demattê, J. A. M., Dionizio, E. A., Silva, D. D. da, Cruz, R. R. P., Moura-Bueno, J. M., Santos, U. J. dos, & Costa, M. H. (2023). Sentinel-1 Imagery Used for Estimation of Soil Organic Carbon by Dual-Polarization SAR Vegetation Indices. *Remote Sensing*, *15(23)*, 5464. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS15235464/S1>
- Schalie, R. Van der, Jeu, R. De, Parinussa, R., Rodríguez-Fernández, N., Kerr, Y., Al-Yaari, A., Wigneron, J.-P., Drusch, M., Schalie, R. Van der, Jeu, R. De, Parinussa, R., Rodríguez-Fernández, N., Kerr, Y., Al-Yaari, A., Wigneron, J.-P., & Drusch, M. (2018). The Effect of Three Different Data Fusion Approaches on the Quality of Soil Moisture Retrievals from Multiple Passive Microwave Sensors. *Remote Sensing 2018, Vol. 10, 10(1)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS10010107>
- Shokati, H., Mashal, M., Noroozi, A., Abkar, A. A., Mirzaei, S., Mohammadi-Doqozloo, Z., Taghizadeh-Mehrjardi, R., Khosravani, P., Nabiollahi, K., & Scholten, T. (2024). Random Forest-Based Soil Moisture Estimation Using Sentinel-2, Landsat-8/9, and UAV-Based Hyperspectral Data. *Remote Sensing*, *16(11)*, 1962. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS16111962/S1>
- Tang, M., Li, W., Gao, X., Wu, P., Li, H., Ling, Q., & Zhang, C. (2022). Land use affects the response of soil moisture and soil temperature to environmental factors in the loess hilly region of China. *PeerJ*, *10*. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.13736>
- Wang, W., Zhang, X., Sun, W., & Huang, M. (2022). A Novel Method of Ship Detection under Cloud Interference for Optical Remote Sensing Images. *Remote Sensing 2022, Vol. 14, Page 3731, 14(15)*, 3731. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS14153731>
- Xiang, X., Li, K., Huang, B., & Cao, Y. (2022). A Multi-Sensor Data-Fusion Method Based on Cloud Model and Improved Evidence Theory. *Sensors 2022, Vol. 22, 22(15)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/S22155902>
- Zhu, F., Wei, H., Shen, Y., Zhang, Y., Xu, N., Zheng, H., Qiao, X., & Liu, D. (2025). A multi-feature fusion based method for detecting the moisture content of withered black tea. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, *141*, 107325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFCA.2025.107325>